

Cardinal-Based Multiphysics Investigation of the MegaPower Heat Pipe Reactor

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ABSTRACT

Heat pipe-cooled microreactors (HPRs) have emerged as a research focus in advanced reactor technologies due to their inherent safety and compact design. However, their high-temperature, solid-core configuration poses significant multiphysics challenges involving coupled neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and structural mechanics. Conventional multiphysics analysis methods often rely on external scripts to link disparate simulation codes, resulting in complex processes that require specialized interface development. To overcome this limitation, this study presents the first full-scale, high-fidelity, steady-state analysis of the megawatt-class MegaPower reactor using the advanced multiphysics code Cardinal. Leveraging the MOOSE framework's MultiApp system, the model integrates the OpenMC Monte Carlo code with MOOSE's mechanics module, orchestrated by a primary thermal-hydraulics application. A robust Picard iteration scheme ensures tight coupling of temperature and displacement feedback effects. The results show that the model accurately predicts core power and temperature distributions, with deviations of less than 1% from reference values. A comparative analysis with a neutronics-thermal (N-T) coupled model demonstrates that the fully coupled neutronics-thermal-mechanical (N-T-M) model, which includes mechanical feedback, introduces a negative reactivity feedback of -437 pcm. Furthermore, the three-dimensional (3D) displacement field under thermal loading was successfully obtained, revealing a deformation pattern fully consistent with physical principles. This work validates Cardinal's powerful capabilities for simulating complex solid-core reactors, establishing it as a high-fidelity, integrated simulation tool for HPR design and safety analysis.

Keywords: Heat Pipe Reactor, Multiphysics Coupling, Cardinal, Neutronics-Thermal-Mechanical

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, advanced reactor technologies, particularly HPRs, have garnered significant attention due to their advantages in inherent safety, structural compactness, and operational flexibility [1]. Following the successful Kilopower Reactor Using Stirling Technology (KRUSTY) experiment at Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) [2], numerous HPR concepts have been proposed, with the MegaPower reactor being a prominent example [3].

Operating at temperatures exceeding 1000 K, the MegaPower reactor experiences significant thermally-induced stresses and structural expansion. These deformations alter core geometry and material densities, introducing critical reactivity feedback that directly impacts reactor safety and control. Consequently, a high-fidelity assessment of the tightly coupled multiphysics interactions among the neutronics, thermal, and stress fields is essential for HPR design and safety analysis. Previous studies have addressed this challenge, but typically by coupling standalone codes via external scripts. For instance, Lee et al. simulated the MegaPower reactor by linking PROTEUS, FLUENT, and ANLHTP with Python scripts to exchange data for power and temperature estimations [4]. Similarly, Im et al. combined PRAGMA, OpenFOAM, and ANLHTP via an external interface for steady-state analysis [5]. While validating the importance of multiphysics coupling, these loosely-coupled approaches are often complex, requiring bespoke development of mesh and data mapping interfaces.

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This study employs Cardinal, an advanced multiphysics application developed on the MOOSE framework [6]. By integrating solvers such as OpenMC and Nek5000, Cardinal enables seamless, tightly-coupled simulations, eliminating the complexities of external interface development. This paper presents a detailed, full-core, steady-state analysis of the MegaPower reactor to determine the coupled equilibrium distributions of key physical fields—power, temperature, and displacement and to quantitatively evaluate the impact of multiphysics effects on overall reactor performance.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. 5MW Heat Pipe Cooled Reactor

The MegaPower, designed by LANL, is a megawatt-class heat pipe-cooled reactor. It has a rated thermal power of 5 MWt (approximately 2 MWe) and features a solid monolithic core design. The primary structure is constructed from 316 stainless steel, which serves as a matrix for the embedded UO₂ fuel rods and heat pipes. The core is composed of six identical trapezoidal sectors. Each sector contains a regular lattice of 204 heat pipes and 352 fuel rods. A central hexagonal channel is reserved for a safety control rod. The core is surrounded by an alumina (Al₂O₃) reflector, within which 12 control drums are embedded. Each drum contains a poison arc made of boron carbide (B₄C), enriched to 90% in ¹⁰B, for reactivity control. More information can be referred the literature [7]

2.2. Cardinal Computational Framework

The numerical simulations were performed using Cardinal, a high-fidelity multiphysics application from Idaho National Laboratory (INL) built on the MOOSE framework. Cardinal is designed to analyze tightly coupled physics, such as neutronics, thermal-hydraulics, and fuel performance. It utilizes the MOOSE MultiApp system to orchestrate these interactions in parallel [8]. This system operates with a primary application overseeing one or more sub-applications, which can themselves contain nested applications, creating a deeply extensible, hierarchical simulation structure.

2.3. Neutronics Model

The neutronics analysis was carried out using the open-source Monte Carlo code OpenMC, developed at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), which has now become a critical tool in nuclear science computation and engineering [9]. Leveraging the hexagonal symmetry of the MegaPower core, a one-sixth sector model was constructed using OpenMC's Constructive Solid Geometry capabilities. The model represents the upper half of the core, as depicted in Figure 1. For a high-fidelity power distribution analysis, this fuel region was further discretized by dividing each of the 352 fuel rods into 10 axial segments, yielding a total of 3,520 tally cells. Reflective boundary conditions were imposed on the three planar symmetry faces and the bottom surface of the sector model. Vacuum boundary conditions were applied to the outer cylindrical boundary and the top surface of the upper reflector.

Figure 1. OpenMC MegaPower model.

2.4. Heat-conduction Model

The thermal analysis in this study employs the steady-state heat conduction module available within the MOOSE framework. This module solves the governing equation for steady-state heat conduction, derived from Fourier's law and the principle of energy conservation:

$$-\nabla \cdot (k_s \nabla T_s) = \dot{q}_s \quad (1)$$

Where k_s represents the thermal conductivity of the solid, T_s is the temperature field, and \dot{q}_s is the volumetric heat source term. In the MegaPower reactor, heat removal is primarily achieved through heat pipes. However, due to the computational impracticality of simulating the complex two-phase heat transfer phenomena inside the heat pipes, and considering their operating temperature of 950.15 K, this simulation applies a fixed temperature boundary condition (Dirichlet BC) of 950.15 K on the outer surface of each heat pipe as a simplified approach.

2.5. Mechanical Computing Model

During the initial stages of the reactor's operational life (Beginning of Life, BOL), structural deformation is dominated by thermal expansion, which induces global displacement of the core. Consequently, the effects of neutron irradiation on material properties and deformation are neglected in this analysis. The mechanical response of the solid components is modeled as a quasi-static process, governed by the mechanical equilibrium equation:

$$\nabla \cdot \sigma + f = 0 \quad (2)$$

Where σ represents the Cauchy strain tensor, f is the body force vector. The thermo-elastic constitutive relation, which links stress to strain, is given by:

$$\sigma = E: (\varepsilon - \varepsilon_T) \quad (3)$$

Where ε represents the total strain tensor, E is the fourth-order elastic stiffness tensor, and ε_T is the thermal strain tensor.

For the structural analysis, fixed boundary conditions are applied to the bottom surface of the model, as well as to the planar (non-arc) side boundaries of the matrix and the outer reflector. The top surface of the core and the curved (arc) boundary of the outer reflector are treated as free surfaces, allowing for unimpeded thermal expansion.

2.6. Multiphysics Coupling Scheme

This study employs the Picard iteration method for multiphysics coupling calculations, achieving convergence through data exchange among neutronics, heat conduction, and structural mechanics models as illustrated in Figure 2. The iterative cycle begins with the neutronics model, which computes the power distribution from a given temperature field and provides power values for each OpenMC fuel cell. This power data is then mapped onto the mesh of the heat conduction model via interpolation. Solving the heat conduction equation yields a high-fidelity nodal temperature field. This new temperature field serves two feedback paths. First, it is passed back to the neutronics model; the average temperature is calculated for each OpenMC cell by identifying the thermal mesh elements whose centroids fall within it and performing a many-to-one mapping to update the material temperatures. Second, the temperature field is fed to the structural mechanics model to compute thermal expansion displacements. Material densities are subsequently updated to conserve mass, with the fuel density being updated directly through its thermophysical correlations. The updated displacement field and material densities are then returned to the heat conduction and neutronics models, respectively, launching the next iteration. The entire process is repeated until all monitored physics quantities converge or the maximum iteration limit is met.

Figure 2. Workflow of the multiphysics coupling analysis model

For mesh generation, the 3D finite element mesh was made using the open-source software Gmsh [10], with the meshing process being programmatic and automated via its Python API, pygmsh. It is noteworthy that, due to the complexity of mesh generation, the helium gap between the fuel pellets and the matrix was not explicitly modeled. Instead, this region was treated as an extension of the matrix material under the assumption of perfect solid-to-solid thermal contact. While neglecting the actual mechanical behavior of the gap may introduce some error in displacement calculations, this simplification is considered acceptable for obtaining the overall temperature distribution and stress state of the reactor. Regarding material density feedback, the density of UO_2 [11] is calculated as a function of temperature using thermophysical correlations. In contrast, the matrix density is continuously updated based on thermal strain, as its temperature increase and corresponding volume change are less significant than those of the fuel.

To ensure simulation accuracy and efficiency, a mesh independence analysis was conducted on a 2D steady-state N-T-M model. Using the same boundary conditions and physical models as the full-scale simulation, the mesh sensitivity study (Figure 3) indicates that a 0.5 cm mesh size is sufficient to meet accuracy requirements. Therefore, this resolution was adopted for the subsequent 3D multiphysics simulations to conserve computational resources.

Figure 3. Results of mesh sensitivity.

3. NUMERICAL RESULT

3.1. Verification

To validate the computational model, the simulation results were benchmarked against the reference data from Sterbentz et al [12]. As illustrated in Figure 4, which compares the temperature distribution in the fuel region, the predicted temperature profile closely matches the reference results. The predicted maximum fuel temperature is 1033.4 K, which differs by 7.8 K from the reference value of 1025.6 K. This discrepancy is likely attributable to differences in the gap conductance models used in the respective simulations. For a clearer understanding of the matrix temperature distribution, Figure 5 presents a comparison of the matrix temperature profile after removing the fuel. The matrix temperature distribution also agrees well with the reference data. The predicted peak matrix temperature (969.6 K) is nearly identical to the benchmark value (969.4 K). In conclusion, these validation results confirm that the computational model developed in this work is highly accurate.

Figure 4. Comparison of the fuel temperature field with that of Sterbentz et al. (units in K).

Figure 5. Comparison of the monolith temperature field with that of Sterbentz et al. (units in K).

3.2. Analysis of Coupled Neutronic-Thermal-Mechanics

To quantify the thermodynamic effects on reactor steady-state characteristics, this study conducted a comparative analysis between the N-T-M model and the N-T coupled model. Given that the power distributions of both models are nearly identical and the temperature field variations are relatively small, the analysis primarily focused on comparing the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} results. As shown in Table I, the k_{eff} of the N-T-M coupling exhibited a significant reduction of 437 pcm compared to the N-T coupling, which is entirely attributable to thermal-mechanical feedback: elevated temperatures cause thermal expansion of core materials, reducing the average fuel density while simultaneously altering core geometry. These combined effects increase neutron leakage probability and decrease absorption, thereby introducing additional negative reactivity.

Table I. The difference between N-T coupling and N-T-M coupling cases.

	N – T coupling	N – T – M coupling	Discrepancy
k_{eff}	1.06062	1.05625	-437pcm

Figure 6 presents the steady-state power distribution within the reactor core, showing both the (a) total power per fuel pin and the (b) 3D power density distribution. The 3D distribution in (b) reveals that the power peaks along the axial centerline, which is furthest from the ends of the core where neutron leakage is minimized. The global maximum power density occurs at the axial center (bottom of the model), with a secondary peak visible near the top due to the neutron-reflecting effect of the top axial reflector.

Complementing this, the radial profile in (a) illustrates a pronounced gradient, with the highest axially-averaged power (> 1500 W) located in the fuel element at the geometric center. Power progressively decreases towards the periphery. Notably, a slight power upturn is observed in the outermost fuel elements, a characteristic phenomenon caused by the side reflector thermalizing and reflecting neutrons back into the core, thereby enhancing the local fission rate at the core-reflector interface.

Figure 6. (a) Radial average power distribution. (b) 3D power density distribution.

The temperature distribution in the reactor core closely aligns with the power distribution, as depicted in Figure 7. The results show that the bulk temperature of the core ranges from approximately 950 K to 1030 K. The temperature distribution closely mirrors the power distribution, exhibiting a profile that is high at the center and low at the periphery radially. Axially, two distinct temperature peaks are observed, analogous to the power profile. The global maximum temperature, or hot spot, is located on the centerline of the central fuel element, coinciding with the axial location of the primary power peak.

Figure 7. 3D temperature distribution. (units in K)

Where the displacement field was not fed back into the simulation due to meshing challenges within the helium gap, the overall displacement field resulting from thermal expansion was nevertheless obtained, as illustrated in Figure 8. The two plots on the left specifically illustrate the directional nature of the displacement, confirming that the structure expands uniformly outwards in the radial direction. The plot on the right displays the magnitude of the total displacement vector. Collectively, the results show that the structure undergoes a pronounced deformation, characterized primarily by axial elongation and radial expansion. This observed deformation pattern corresponds directly to the internal temperature distribution of the reactor core, which features a hot central region and a cooler periphery.

Figure 8. UX, UY and total displacement distributions.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study employs the Cardinal code to establish a multiphysics coupling model for the MegaPower heat pipe reactor, simulating the neutronics-thermal-structural interactions within the reactor core

assembly. The full-scale model accurately reproduces the power and temperature distributions in the core, with calculated maximum temperatures of both fuel and matrix materials deviating less than 1% from experimental values. Compared to neutronics-thermal coupling alone, the incorporation of thermal expansion-induced changes in material density and geometry introduces a negative reactivity feedback of -437 pcm. The computed displacement field exhibits an outward expansion pattern from the center to both ends, with its deformation mode perfectly aligned with the internal temperature gradient distribution, which is consistent with physical expectations.

A key limitation of this study is that the calculated displacements were not used to deform the computational mesh. Consequently, the UO₂ material density was updated using temperature-dependent correlations rather than being derived from the volumetric strain of the deformed mesh. This approach means that the mass within each mesh element is not explicitly conserved with respect to its geometric deformation, a limitation to be addressed in future work.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. H. Yan, C. Wang, and L. G. Li, "The technology of micro heat pipe cooled reactor: A review," *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 135, Art. no. 106948, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2019.106948.
- [2] M. Gibson, D. Poston, P. McClure, T. Godfroy, J. Sanzi, and M. Briggs, "The Kilowatt Reactor Using Stirling Technology (KRUSTY) Nuclear Ground Test Results and Lessons Learned," presented at the AIAA Propulsion and Energy 2018 Forum, Cincinnati, OH, USA, Jul. 2018, Art. no. AIAA 2018-4973, doi: 10.2514/6.2018-4973.
- [3] P. R. McClure, D. I. Poston, V. R. Dasari, and R. S. Reid, "Design of megawatt power level heat pipe reactors," Los Alamos National Lab. (LANL), Los Alamos, NM, USA, Rep. LA-UR-15-28840, Nov. 2015. doi: 10.2172/1226133.
- [4] C. Lee, Y. S. Jung, and H. K. Cho, "Micro Reactor Simulation Using the PROTEUS Suite in FY19," Argonne National Lab. (ANL), Argonne, IL, USA, Rep. ANS/NSE-19/33, Sep. 2019. doi: 10.2172/1571248.
- [5] J. Im, M. J. Jeong, N. Choi, K. M. Kim, H. K. Cho, and H. G. Joo, "Multiphysics Analysis System for Heat Pipe-Cooled Micro Reactors Employing PRAGMA-OpenFOAM-ANLHTP," *Nucl. Sci. Eng.*, vol. 197, no. 8, pp. 1743–1757, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1080/00295639.2022.2143209.
- [6] A. J. Novak, H. Brooks, P. Shriwise, A. Hegazy, and A. Davis. "Multiphysics Coupling of OpenMC CAD-Based Transport to MOOSE using Cardinal and Aurora." In *Proceedings of M&C 2023 - International Conference on Mathematics & Computational Methods Applied to Nuclear Science & Engineering*, Niagara Falls, Canada (2023). URL <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/373157683>
- [7] Y. Ma et al., "Transient heat pipe failure accident analysis of a megawatt heat pipe cooled reactor," *Prog. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 140, Art. no. 103904, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.pnucene.2021.103904.
- [8] E. Merzari et al. "Cardinal: A Lower Length-Scale Multiphysics Simulator for Pebble-Bed Reactors." *Nuclear Technology*. doi: 10.1080/00295450.2020.1824471
- [9] Y. Wang, Y. Ma, and N. Jiang, "Steady state neutronic and thermal-mechanical coupling analysis of inelastic deformation in solid-state heat pipe cooled reactor," *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 208, Art. no. 110802, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2024.110802.
- [10] C. Geuzaine and J.-F. Remacle. *Gmsh: General Overview and Recent Developments*. Université de Liège and Université catholique de Louvain (2023). URL <https://gmsh.info>
- [11] S. G. Popov and J. J. Carbajo, "Thermophysical Properties of MOX and UO₂ Fuels Including the Effects of Irradiation," Oak Ridge National Lab. (ORNL), Oak Ridge, TN, USA, Rep. ORNL/TM-2000/351, Feb. 2001.
- [12] J. W. Sterbentz et al., "Special Purpose Nuclear Reactor (5 MW) for Reliable Power at Remote Sites Assessment Report," Idaho National Lab. (INL), Idaho Falls, ID, USA, Rep. INL/EXT-16-40741, Apr. 2017. doi: 10.2172/1410224.